

Estimation of the compression capacity of round bamboo columns considering the relationship between mechanical properties and culm geometry

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Abstract

This study aims to establish an estimation method for the compression strength of full-culm bamboo columns by conducting buckling tests on small-scale specimens and comparing the results with theoretical formulations. The bending Young's modulus and crushing strength are experimentally evaluated, and their relationships with culm diameter are analyzed using regression equations. The results indicate a strong negative correlation between culm diameter and Young's modulus, while the correlation with crushing strength varies between bamboo species. Following above, the study verifies the accuracy of Ylinen's formula for estimating compression strength, showing that when mechanical properties are accurately evaluated, predictions align well with experimental results. However, variability in crushing strength introduces uncertainty, highlighting the need for further refinement of estimation methods. The findings suggest that incorporating gradient characteristics of material properties can improve the practicality of design formulations.

Keywords: round bamboo, full-culm bamboo, bamboo structures, compression capacity, buckling strength, cross-sectional variation, gradient mechanical properties, Ylinen's formula.

1. Introduction

Bamboo has a short harvesting cycle, strong regenerative capacity, and remarkable carbon sequestration ability, along with excellent mechanical properties, making it a highly promising material for sustainable construction. Looking ahead, as the world aims to achieve a carbon-neutral society, bamboo is increasingly regarded as a viable alternative for construction materials. However, numerous challenges remain in utilizing bamboo as a structural material. In particular, the urgent task of standardizing various design strengths must be addressed. Accurately evaluating the design compression capacity is essential for using round bamboo (full-culm bamboo) as columns or truss elements. However, due to the significant variability and uncertainties in material properties, the current formulations in major bamboo structural design standards, such as ISO 22156[1] and NSR-10 [2], are considered overly conservative compared to experimental results (Harries et al. [3]). For instance, Harries et al. [3] investigated the relationship between cross-sectional variations, gradient characteristics of mechanical properties, and buckling strength of bamboo culms, arguing that using the minimum cross-section to calculate design compression capacity is excessively conservative. Additionally, Nagai and Oki [4] demonstrated a clear negative correlation between cross-sectional size and bending modulus of elasticity in bamboo culms, which should be considered when evaluating buckling strength.

In this study, based on compression tests conducted on small-scale round bamboo columns, we formulate the gradient characteristics of cross-sectional variations and bending Young's modulus

along the culm axis and verify the accuracy of a compression capacity estimation formula based on existing strength formulations. It should be noted that this paper reintroduces and discusses the experimental results presented in Nagai and Oki [4] for further analysis.

2. Bamboo materials

The distribution and total amount of bamboo forest resources in Japan indicate that approximately 99% of the 150,000 hectares of bamboo forest area is occupied by Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys edulis*) and Madake (*Phyllostachys bambusoides*), with a ratio of roughly 3:1 (Inoue et al. [5]). Although Hachiku (*Phyllostachys nigra*) is locally abundant in certain regions, it accounts for only about 0.4% of the total bamboo forest area in Japan. Therefore, Moso bamboo and Madake are the primary bamboo species that should be considered when discussing the utilization of Japan's bamboo forest resources.

This study focuses on two bamboo species: domestically grown Moso bamboo and Madake. All specimens were harvested in 2022 from a bamboo forest in Ōmihachiman-city, Shiga Prefecture (35.15°N, 136.09°E). In this forest, Moso bamboo and Madake grow in adjacent stands. The bamboo specimens were selected to be at least three years old, and their ages were visually determined based on surface color and other external characteristics. The culm diameters at breast height were categorized into three groups: 60–80 mm, 80–100 mm, and over 100 mm. After harvesting, the bamboo specimens were air-dried in a well-ventilated semi-outdoor storage area, protected from direct rainfall. Various measurements, processing, and mechanical tests were conducted within a few months after harvesting. Since the storage period after harvesting was short, no protective treatment was applied to the bamboo.

3. Methods of investigation

3.1. Experimental procedure

Bamboo culms are variable cross-sectional members, with their cross-sectional dimensions changing along the culm axis. Therefore, they cannot be modeled as simple homogeneous and uniform cross-sectional members. In this study, to estimate the buckling strength of round bamboo columns, a finite element model that accounts for cross-sectional variations is used, and a linear buckling analysis is performed. During this process, the cross-sectional dimensions and the bending Young's modulus of each section of the bamboo culm are required, so experiments and measurements are carried out following the steps below.

First, bending tests are conducted on round bamboo columns to determine the bending stiffness from the load-deformation relationship. The bending tests involve small deformation bending to ensure that the stress and strain in the test specimens remain within the elastic range, thereby preventing plastic deformation in the samples. Next, to minimize changes in moisture content, buckling tests are conducted promptly. In this study, due to constraints in testing equipment, experiments are conducted on small-scale specimens with a constant column length. After the buckling tests, the bamboo culms are cut at the midpoint of each internode to measure cross-sectional dimensions. The test specimens were selected to ensure that their effective slenderness ratios were uniformly distributed within the range of 40–150. A total of 55 Madake specimens and 38 Moso bamboo specimens were tested.

3.2. Small deformation bending test

Fig. 1 illustrates the testing method. The bending test was conducted using a three-point bending setup, with the load applied at the center of the span. The two support points were positioned to avoid bamboo nodes and were placed near the midpoint of the internodes. To determine the average bending Young's modulus over the entire specimen length, the support positions were set to maximize the span. Additionally, in accordance with ISO 22157 [6], the shear span ratio was maintained at 10 or

greater. As a result, the span length between the supports varied among specimens, ranging from approximately 1,600 mm to 2,000 mm. The experiment was terminated when any of the following conditions were met: (1) the applied load reached 250 N, (2) the deflection at the loading point reached 1/200 of the span between supports, (3) the bending stress at the central loading point reached 30 N/mm². The upper limit of the bending stress was set to approximately one-third of the bending strength of Moso bamboo and Madake (approximately 100 N/mm²) (Nagai [7]). The bending stress was calculated by measuring the culm diameter D at the midpoint of the span before testing. The culm wall thickness t was empirically estimated as follows: Madake: $t = 0.06D$, Moso bamboo: $t = 0.08D$. The calculated section modulus based on these assumptions was used in the stress calculation. After the bending tests, it was confirmed that none of the specimens exhibited any damage, cracks, or residual deformation.

Figure 1. Method of small deformation bending test of round bamboo columns.

3.3. Buckling test

Fig. 2(a) shows the method of the buckling test for round bamboo columns. After the bending test, the specimens were processed to a length of 1,600 mm in accordance with the testing machine's specifications. Spherical seats made of aluminum alloy were provided at the upper and lower loading points, serving as pin supports. The loading speed was controlled using load regulation, ensuring that the maximum load was reached approximately 5 minutes after the start of the test.

Figure 2. (a) Buckling test method for round bamboo columns, (b) method of short-column compression test for round bamboo.

3.4. Short-column compression and other mechanical tests

Following the buckling tests, additional mechanical tests were conducted promptly to minimize changes in moisture content. Multiple specimens were extracted without damage from the tested bamboo columns and subjected to short-column compression tests, shear tests, and transverse bending tests. Among these, the short-column compression strength (hereinafter referred to as crushing strength) is directly relevant to the estimation of the compression capacity of round bamboo columns.

Therefore, only the results of this test are presented in this paper. The testing method for the short-column compression test is illustrated in Fig. 2(b). Additionally, the mass of each specimen was measured immediately before each mechanical test. After testing, moisture content measurements were conducted without delay.

3.5. Calculation of compression strength using Ylinen's formula

Internationally recognized methods for calculating the compression strength of round bamboo columns include the structural design code NSR-10 [2] in Colombia and ISO 22156 [1], listed in chronological order of their establishment. Among these, the latter provides a more detailed design framework by considering factors such as load duration and environmental conditions, and it is expected to become the standard formulation in the future. The compression capacity P_{cr} in ISO 22156 is based on Ylinen's formula (Zahn [8]). Unlike many other strength formulas, which categorize slenderness ratios into short, intermediate, and long columns, Ylinen's formula has the advantage of covering the entire slenderness ratio range with a single equation. Additionally, it is characterized by its ability to represent mixed-mode failure, where both plastic and elastic buckling coexist, using only a single coefficient, c . The compression strength P_{cr} in ISO 22156 is given as follows:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{P_c + P_e}{2c} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{P_c + P_e}{2c}\right)^2 - \frac{P_c \cdot P_e}{c}} \quad (1)$$

Here, P_c represents the crushing capacity, and P_e represents the elastic buckling capacity. These values are determined as follows:

$$P_c = f_c \sum A \quad (2)$$

$$P_e = \frac{n\pi^2 E_d I_{\min} C_{bow}}{(KL)^2} \quad \text{or} \quad P_e = \frac{n\pi^2 (EI)_{d,\min} C_{bow}}{(KL)^2} \quad (3)$$

where n : the number of bamboo members constituting the column, E_d : the design elastic modulus, I_{\min} : the smallest second moment of area among the bamboo members constituting the column, $(EI)_{d,\min}$: the smallest bending stiffness among the bamboo members constituting the column, C_{bow} : a reduction factor accounting for the initial imperfection of the bamboo column, KL : the effective buckling length. In this study, since the column consists of a single bamboo culm, we set $n = 1$. Additionally, when both ends of the column are simply supported, $KL = L$. The factor C_{bow} is a knockdown factor that reduces the buckling capacity when the ratio of lateral bowing to the effective buckling length exceeds 1/50. However, since the bamboo specimens used in the experiment were selected to have minimal initial imperfections, $C_{bow} = 1$ is assumed in this study. Therefore, in this paper, P_c is determined from the crushing strength of the bamboo culm, while P_e is calculated using the Young's modulus obtained from the small deformation bending test, and these values are then substituted into Eq. (1) to determine the theoretical compression strength P_{cr} . Furthermore, P_e is defined as the first-mode linear buckling load obtained through linear buckling analysis using an FEM model, which is constructed based on the measured dimensions of the bamboo culm.

3.6. FEM modeling and analysis of bamboo culms

Fig. 3(a) shows the method used to measure the geometric properties of the bamboo culms used as test specimens. The measured parameters include the internode length L_{IN} , the culm diameter D , and the culm wall thickness t at the midpoint of the internodes. These measurements are taken after the buckling tests by cutting and examining the relevant sections. The diameter D is obtained by measuring the outer circumference at the midpoint of the internode using a tape measure and dividing it by π . Although the actual cross-section of a bamboo culm is not a perfect circle, in this study, all

calculations assume a circular cross-section with diameter D . The wall thickness t is determined as the average of four measurements taken at orthogonal points (N, E, S, W) on the cross-section.

Fig. 3(b) illustrates the method for constructing an FEM model for calculating the bending Young's modulus. In this model, nodes are placed at the positions of the bamboo culm's nodes, and these nodes are connected by planar (2D) beam elements with a uniform cylindrical cross-section. The sectional properties of these beam elements are based on the measured cross-sectional dimensions at the midpoint of the internodes. As a result, the FEM model approximates the variation in cross-sectional properties along the culm axis in a stepwise manner. Additional nodes are assigned at the loading point in the middle of the span and at both support positions. The boundary conditions are set as a pinned support at one end and a roller support at the other.

Fig. 3(c) shows the method for constructing an FEM model for buckling analysis. This model is based on the bending analysis model, with additional nodes placed at the center of each internode to refine the buckling mode shapes. The boundary conditions remain the same as those in the bending analysis model, with a pinned support at one end and a roller support at the other.

It is important to note that bamboo nodes act as constraints against the flattening of the cross-section under significant bending. However, in the case of microscopic deformations, their effect is small enough to be ignored. Therefore, in this study, the nodes are disregarded, and the bamboo culm is modeled as a simple hollow cylinder.

Figure 3. Method for measuring culm geometries and FEM modeling for round bamboo columns.

Using the models constructed following the above procedures, the bending Young's modulus for each test specimen is first determined. Using the model as shown in Fig. 3(b), linear stress analysis is performed by applying a concentrated load and simple support boundary conditions at the same nodal positions as in the small deformation bending test. The Young's modulus E_b is adjusted such that the stiffness (load/displacement) at the loading node matches the slope of the linear portion of the experimental load-deformation curve. Next, the obtained E_b is used to perform linear buckling analysis on the FEM model shown in Fig. 3(c), in which axial forces are applied at both ends of the model. The first-mode linear buckling load is then obtained [Note].

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Bending Young's modulus and crushing strength

Fig. 4 illustrates the relationship between culm diameter D , bending Young's modulus E_b , and crushing strength f_c . The bamboo specimens used in the buckling experiments are marked in color (undried), while the gray marks (dried) represent the experimental results obtained by Nagai [9] using

specimens that had reached equilibrium moisture content for comparison. The solid lines in the figure represent regression equations derived using the least squares method. Additionally, Table 1 summarizes the correlation coefficient (CC) between culm diameter and each mechanical property, along with the linear regression equations.

In the clear negative correlation is observed between D and E_b , indicating that E_b decreases linearly as D increases. The correlation coefficient exceeds 0.85 for both species, indicating a strong correlation. Additionally, for both species, the slope of the “undried” data is smaller than that of the “dried” data, suggesting that the rate of change in E_b with respect to D is more gradual in undried bamboo.

Figure 4. Relationship between culm diameter, bending Young's modulus, and crushing strength.

Table 1. Correlation factor between culm diameter and mechanical properties.

species	D vs E_b				D vs f_c			
	undried		dried		undried		dried	
	CC	LRE [GPa]	CC	LRE [GPa]	CC	LRE [MPa]	CC	LRE [MPa]
Madake	-0.86	$E_b = -0.1391D + 23.7$	-0.94	$E_b = -0.2533D + 30.5$	-0.03	$f_c = -0.0149D + 63.8$	-0.35	$f_c = -0.1993D + 97.8$
Moso bamboo	-0.91	$E_b = -0.1579D + 23.3$	-0.95	$E_b = -0.1970D + 25.1$	-0.67	$f_c = -0.4253D + 99.2$	-0.78	$f_c = -0.4161D + 109.6$

D: culm diameter [mm], E_b : Bending Young's modulus [GPa], f_c : crushing strength [MPa], CC: Correlation coefficient, LRE: Linear regression equation

Figure 5. Failure modes in short-column compression tests: left and middle: mode A, right: mode B.

Regarding the relationship between D and f_c , in Madake (undried), the correlation coefficient is low, and the data exhibit significant scatter. In contrast, in Moso bamboo (undried), a clear negative correlation is observed. Additionally, for both bamboo species, as drying progresses, the overall crushing strength f_c increases, and the correlation coefficient with D also improves. Short-column compression tests tend to exhibit high variability due to differences in culm diameter, diameter-to-wall thickness ratio, or the presence of microscopic cracks, which influence the failure mode. Fig. 5 presents examples of failure modes in dried and undried bamboo specimens. For well-dried bamboo, the short-column failure mode typically follows “Mode A”, where the entire bamboo culm expands circumferentially and then splits vertically, after which the individual fiber bundles buckle globally, leading to the maximum load. In contrast, in undried bamboo, the specimen often exhibits local

buckling at an intermediate height before splitting vertically, reaching the maximum load at this stage (“Mode B”). This results in a lower compression capacity compared to mode A. Mode A tends to occur in short to intermediate-length columns with low slenderness ratios and is closely related to compression strength. Mode B is more likely to occur in intermediate to long columns with high slenderness ratios, where global buckling precedes failure. Therefore, mode B is not necessarily decisive for the maximum compression capacity of the column.

4.2. Results of the buckling test

Fig. 6 presents an example of the load–displacement relationship from the buckling test, while Fig. 7 illustrates examples of failure modes observed in the test. All bamboo specimens used in this buckling test were undried materials. The slenderness ratio shown in the figures was calculated using the average culm diameter and culm wall thickness measured at both ends of each specimen. The axial deformation represents the vertical stroke of the testing machine.

For specimens with a small culm diameter and a high slenderness ratio, stiffness gradually decreases before reaching the maximum load, after which the load decreases gradually, leading to large deformations. Eventually, local buckling occurs at approximately mid-height of the column, resulting in failure as shown in Fig. 7(a). Conversely, for specimens with a large culm diameter and a low slenderness ratio, the load increases almost linearly up to the maximum load. After reaching the maximum load, the load rapidly decreases, followed by an explosive failure in which the bamboo column splits into thin strips along the culm axis as shown in Fig. 7(b).

Figure 6. Example of load–displacement relationships in buckling tests.

Figure 7. Differences in failure modes depending on slenderness ratio, (a) local buckling failure mode following global buckling, (b) whole-length crushing mode following global buckling.

Fig. 8 compares the buckling test results for each specimen with the theoretical compression strength values. In all cases, the horizontal axis represents the maximum load P_{max} obtained from the buckling test, while the vertical axis represents the compression strength P_{cr} calculated using Ylinen’s formula and the linear buckling load P_e . The values of P_{cr} and P_e were calculated using the crushing strength f_c and the bending Young’s modulus E_b obtained from mechanical tests for each specimen. The solid

black line in the figure represents the boundary where P_{max} matches with theoretical value. Additionally, Table 2 summarizes the mean values and coefficients of variation (COV) for the ratios P_{cr}/P_{max} and P_e/P_{max} . For Madake, the experimental values align more closely with P_e than with P_{cr} , with an average P_e/P_{max} ratio of 0.97. For Moso bamboo, the theoretical value P_{cr} matches well with P_{max} , with an average P_{cr}/P_{max} ratio of 1.04.

Figure 8. Comparison of maximum load in buckling tests and theoretical compression strength values.

Table 2. Ratio of theoretical compression strength values to maximum load in buckling tests.

species	P_{cr}/P_{max}		P_e/P_{max}	
	Mean	COV	Mean	COV
Madake	0.86	0.31	0.98	0.30
Moso bamboo	1.04	0.22	1.14	0.21

As shown in Fig. 4(b), one reason why the theoretical compressive strength P_{cr} of Madake is generally lower than the experimental values is that the crushing strength f_c of undried Madake was smaller than the typical strength of dried Madake (Nagai [9]). In short-column compression tests on undried bamboo, local buckling of the culm occurs frequently, and the resulting failure mode tends to reduce the crushing strength compared to dried specimens. In contrast, in the buckling test specimens, the presence of nodes restrains local buckling, making it less likely to occur even in undried bamboo. Therefore, the crushing strength obtained from short-column tests on undried bamboo may not be appropriate as an explanatory factor for evaluating plastic buckling in the low slenderness ratio range, and may underestimate the actual buckling strength of the column.

Even in Madake, specimens with large slenderness ratios and low load capacity (e. g. below 20 kN in Fig. 8(a)) show a trend where P_{cr} approaches P_{max} . This suggests that, if the mechanical properties of the material are appropriately evaluated, the ratio of theoretical to experimental values would generally approach unity.

4.3. Estimation of compression strength for round bamboo columns

The compression strength of round bamboo columns was estimated using the regression equations derived from the relationship between culm diameter and mechanical properties obtained from mechanical tests, and its accuracy was evaluated. The estimated buckling strength f_{cr} was calculated by substituting the regression equations for undried bamboo from Table 1 into Eq. (1) to obtain P_{cr} , which was then divided by the cross-sectional area. For the calculation of the slenderness ratio λ , the average cross-sectional area A_{av} and the average second moment of area I_{av} were determined using the average culm diameter and culm wall thickness measured at both ends of the bamboo column. The effective buckling length was fixed at 1,600 mm for all specimens.

Fig. 9 illustrates the relationship between slenderness ratio and compression strength. f_{cr} : estimated compression strength, obtained using the method described above, f_{max} : experimental compression strength, calculated as P_{max}/A_{av} from the maximum load P_{max} in the buckling test, and f_e : elastic buckling strength, calculated as P_e/A_{av} . For Madake, f_{cr} ($f_{c,dried}$) represents the estimated compression strength when using the $D-E_b$ regression equation for dried bamboo. Since the crushing strength f_c obtained from the dried regression equation is higher than that from the undried $D-f_c$ relationship, f_{cr} is slightly closer to the elastic buckling strength f_e . Table 3 summarizes the mean values and coefficients of variation for the ratio f_{cr}/f_{max} between the estimated and experimental compression strengths. For Madake, the agreement between f_{cr} and f_{max} improves when using the regression equation for the crushing strength of dried bamboo rather than that for undried bamboo. For Moso bamboo, the estimated values tend to be slightly higher, but the error remains within approximately 15%. These results suggest that the average buckling strength of round bamboo columns can be estimated with high accuracy using regression equations where culm diameter is the only explanatory variable.

However, when using regression equations with culm diameter as the sole parameter, the prediction accuracy exhibits significant variability. This is because the correlation between culm diameter and crushing strength is much weaker than that between culm diameter and Young's modulus. Therefore, when estimating the compression strength of round bamboo columns based on culm diameter, it is necessary to consider the variability in crushing strength and determine an appropriate safety factor.

Figure 9. Comparison of approximated compression strength equations with experimental results.

Table 3. Ratio of estimated compression strength to experimental values.

species	$f_{cr}(f_c,undried)/f_{max}$		$f_{cr}(f_c,dried)/f_{max}$	
	Mean	COV	Mean	COV
Madake	0.96	0.43	1.00	0.44
Moso bamboo	1.14	0.35	—	—

5. Conclusion

In this study, we aimed to establish a method for estimating the compression strength of round bamboo (full-culm bamboo) columns. To achieve this, we conducted buckling tests on small-scale specimens and evaluated their related mechanical properties, comparing the experimental results with the compression strength estimation formula based on Ylinen's formula.

The findings indicate that if the short-column compression strength and bending Young's modulus of bamboo are accurately assessed in advance, the compression strength of round bamboo columns can be estimated with high accuracy using the theoretical equation. On the other hand, when the crushing strength and Young's modulus are estimated using regression equations with culm diameter as the sole parameter, the average compression strength of bamboo columns can be predicted with reasonable accuracy. However, significant variability is observed. This is because the correlation between culm diameter and Young's modulus is strong, whereas the relationship between culm diameter and

crushing strength exhibits greater variability, as the failure mode in crushing varies across multiple mechanisms.

Based on these findings, the following key challenges need to be addressed to improve the estimation of compression strength in round bamboo columns: 1) identifying geometric parameters or physical constants that better explain crushing strength, 2) classifying failure modes in crushing and determining the appropriate strength values for each mode, and 3) conducting extensive experimental studies to evaluate variability and determine appropriate safety factors.

In addition to these challenges, further research is required to develop a reliable method for calculating the design compression strength of round bamboo columns, taking into account initial imperfections, boundary conditions, service environments, and long-term usage effects.

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Note

The Young's modulus and linear buckling load obtained from FEM analysis showed no significant difference compared to the results of a perfect cylindrical model that assumed a uniform cross-section, using the average culm diameter and culm wall thickness measured at both ends of the bamboo culm. Within the length range of the Madake and Moso bamboo specimens used in this study (maximum approximately 1.6 m), assuming the bamboo culm as a uniform cylindrical cross-section does not appear to pose a major issue.

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